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Deformation Mechanism Investigation for Epoxy by In-situ Electrical and Mechanics Coupling Measurement

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A. G. Varghese, R. C. Batra, Constitutive equations for thermomechanical deformations of glassy polymers, Int J Solids Struct, 2009, 46, (22-23): 4079-4094

MATERIALS

Epoxy-matric composite with 0.0 and 3.0 wt.% of CNT

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy
an epoxide equivalent weight of 185 g/mol (E51)
the curing agent 593 from Shanghai Resin Factory Co., Ltd.

Carbon nanotube Pristine CVD-multi-walled carbon
nanotubes (CNTs) with diameter 60 nm and average length
of 3 μm from Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co. Ltd, China.

Fabrication process as the following procedure:

3g CNTs are dispersed in 100 g acetone by mechanical stirring for 15 min, followed by ultra-sonication for 30 min. Then 100 g epoxy (E51) is added to the suspension and mixed evenly. Then curing agent 593 is added into the suspensions and stirred for 5 minutes. Then the mixtures are poured into a polypropylene mold and cured at room temperature for 2 h, followed by another 4 h at 80 °C, then the CNT nanocomposite is fabricated. In addition, pure epoxy bulk is also fabricated.

SPECIMEN

Cylindrical specimen: $\text{Ø}4.0 \text{ mm} \times 4.0 \text{ mm}$

Bulk materials, fabricated from the
below-mentioned procedure, are cut into
 $\text{Ø}4.0 \text{ mm} \times 4.0 \text{ mm}$ cylindrical specimens
for mechanical experimental study.

Eletro-mech coupling meas.

Figure 1 Schematic map of specimen resistance measurement (A), and the experimental picture of compression test where the glass pads are used for shielding potential interference (B).

$$R = \rho \frac{l}{S} \Rightarrow \rho = \frac{R \cdot S}{l} = \frac{R \cdot V}{l^2} = \frac{R \cdot V}{l_0^2 \cdot (1 - \varepsilon)} \quad (1)$$

Eletro-mech coupling behaviors

Figure 2 Origin experimental data of CNT composite under compressive loading: (A) load-displacement curve and (B) the corresponding specimen voltage signal, and calculated stress-strain curve and volume resistivity curve during deforming.

Mechanical measurement

Figure 3 Stress-strain curves of epoxy under different strains (A) with the previous three experiments below peak stress, and (B) with the previous nine experiments over peak stress.

$$E_{si} = \frac{E_{ith}}{E_1} \quad (2)$$

where E_j is the elastic modulus of the first load for each specimen involved, and E_{si} was the specific elastic modulus of the ith load, with $i=2,3$, until to 10.

Interrelation between peak stress and elastic modulus

Figure 4 Specific elastic modulus comparisons for prior to, beyond peak stress.

Predicted mechanism:

The evolution process is predicted in details as follows: when the external stress is applied to the three-dimension crosslinking epoxy, the bond length, valence angles, and other short chain units start to cooperative motion for the reversible deformation prior to the peak stress. With the deformation continuing up to peak stress of specimen, the stress concentration occurs in some crosslinking sites, due to the void, molecular structure singularity under stressed and even some inclusion et al. Once crosslinking sites break, then more molecular chain units are freed which are previously constrained by these sites. Then the chain segments are formed by those freed chain units, and start to motion due to the external loads. The breaking of crosslinking sites and the coordinated motion of more chain units join in the cooperative deformation, and then the deformation resistance of specimen will be weakening, and result in strain softening phenomenon in macroscopic view. With the specimen further deformation, some of the residual crosslinking sites are stressed to break due to the same factor. Then it induces the further weakening, namely continuous strain softening.

Figure 4 Normalized stress-strain curves characteristics of pure epoxy and CNT nanocomposite.

Figure 6 Deformation and microstructure evolution process of nanocomposite.

The mechanism verified by the resistivity of CNT nanocomposite:

The mechanism is predicted for the matrix epoxy of nanocomposite that the cross-linked sites are about to break when the specimen is loaded to peak stress, and the more molecular chain units freed from the broken sites can form the molecular segments to cooperative motion of molecular microstructure. Accordingly, the conductive network of CNT is partly destroyed, and then some conductive passageways are interrupted. Furthermore, the second electrical conductivity mechanism: electron hopping will be partly limited. Due to the sites' breakage, the distance between CNTs will widen. Then the resistivity will increase distinctly due to its high dependence of electron hopping on the separation distance between CNTs. Thus, the resistivity will start to sharply increase since the peak strain as shown in Fig. 2 (C).

